

DEMONSTRATION OF A NOVEL HIGH PRESSURE VESSEL STRUCTURE CONSISTING OF CFRP OVERWRAPPED CYLINDER AND BELT SHAPED LOAD MEMBERS FOR FUEL CELL VEHICLES

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ABSTRACT

Cost reduction of CFRP hydrogen tanks is important to promote the practical use of fuel cell vehicles. In this study, in order to achieve a significant reduction in the amount of carbon fiber used, a "multi-load path structure" is proposed in which the axial and circumferential loads acting on the tank are shared by different members: CFRP overwrapped cylinder and belt shaped load members. For the purpose of technically verifying the structural concept, stress analysis, design and prototyping were carried out for a tank structure that uses two belt-shaped axial load members, and a structural strength evaluation was carried out by burst tests. As a result, it was demonstrated that it is possible to realize a tank structure that has a burst pressure almost as designed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Type-IV 70 MPa class high-pressure hydrogen tanks, in which carbon fiber is wound around a polymer liner by the filament winding (FW) method, have been applied to commercially available fuel cell vehicles (FCVs) [1, 2]. In order to expand the use of FCVs, in addition to reducing the cost and improving the productivity of hydrogen tanks, it is necessary to improve the packaging capability of the tanks to automobiles. To improve the packaging capability of the tanks, the concept of a "multiple tank module" has been proposed [3]. In the tanks made by FW method, low-angle helical winding must be applied to form the dome section, but there is a tendency for excess carbon fiber to be generated in the cylinder section. This tendency is more pronounced in small-diameter, long tanks, and simply combining the FW tanks will result in increased costs and reduced weight efficiency due to the increased amount of carbon fiber used. In order to commercialize a tank module with multiple small-diameter, long tanks, it is necessary to significantly reduce the amount of carbon fiber used.

Therefore, this study aims to achieve a significant reduction in the amount of carbon fiber used by applying a "multi-load path structure" in which the axial load and circumferential load acting on the tank are borne by different members. In this structure, the "axial load member" that bears the axial load and the "CFRP overwrapped cylinder" that bears the hoop load are manufactured separately, and then assembled into an integrated tank. It is possible to design the tank so that most of the carbon fibers reach their breaking strain at the same internal pressure when the tank bursts. Therefore, in the case of a small-diameter, long tank, it is possible to reduce the amount of carbon fiber used by more than 30 % compared to a FW tank. In addition, the axial member and cylinder have simple shapes, so productivity is also excellent. If a small-diameter, long tank with a multi-load path structure is realized, it is possible to significantly reduce the cost increase associated with connecting tanks and realize a tank structure with

excellent packaging capabilities at low cost. A similar concept to the multi-load path structure in this study was proposed in a German patent publication [4, 5], but no design considerations or technical demonstrations using tanks have been reported within the scope of the authors' investigation.

In this paper, we report on the results of stress analysis, design, and prototype fabrication of a tank structure that uses two belt-shaped axial load members, as well as the results of a structural strength evaluation conducted by a burst test, with the aim of technically demonstrating the multi-load path structure concept.

(a) Over view

(b) Cross-sectional view

Fig. 1 Schematic drawing of a tank structure consisting of UD-CFRP axial load member and CFRP overlapped cylinder

2. STRESS ANALYSES AND DESIGN

2.1 BASIC CONCEPT OF TANK STRUCTURE

The basic structure and cross-section of the tank used in this study are presented in Fig. 1(a) and (b). The external appearance is similar to the basic structure illustrated in the references [4, 5], but the detailed structure is significantly different. The components are an aluminum alloy (A6061-T6) liner (outer diameter ϕ 99 \times length 272 \times thickness 2.5-9.5 mm), a hoop CFRP layer (CF/Epoxy, thickness

1.6-3.6 mm), an aluminum alloy (A6061-T6) tank head, and two CFRP belt-shaped axial load members (width 25, thickness 2.4, curvature of the arc section 50 mm). The circumferential stress (hoop stress) in the cylinder due to internal pressure is mainly borne by the CFRP hoop layer overwrapped around the Al liner. The axial load acting on the cylinder is borne by two UD-CFRP belt-like axial load members. The tank head (A6061-T6) has a structure in which the dome and boss are integrated. The belt-like axial load members are made of unidirectional CFRP (CF/Epoxy) and are fitted around the top and bottom of the tank head. A high-pressure packing (NOK, Japan) is used as a water tight seal between the outer circumference of the liner and the inner circumference of the tank head.

In this structure, there is a small clearance between the axial load member and the tank head because of mechanical assembling. Therefore, even if an axial load member is applied to a Type III tank that uses a typical dome-cylinder integrated aluminum alloy liner, an axial load will also act directly on the cylinder due to the internal pressure load. In this case, since CFRP is not applied in the axial direction of the cylinder, there is a concern that the cylinder will break in the axial direction at low pressure. Therefore, it is important structural feature that the domes on both sides of the aluminum liner are eliminated, making it a cylindrical liner so that the internal pressure acts directly on the inside of the dome of the tank head.

2. 2 STRESS ANALYSES OF TANK STRUCTURE

A commercial code, ABAQUS/ Standard 2023 (Dassault Systems), was used for the finite element analysis (FEA). The material of the liner and tank head was an aluminum alloy (A6061-T6), and the hoop layer and axial load members were made of unidirectional CFRP (T800/Epoxy, Mizuno Technics, Japan). The mechanical properties of the CFRP used in the analysis are shown in Table 1. The stress-strain curve of the aluminum alloy (A6061-T6) was based on literature values [6], and an elastic-plastic model according to the associated flow rule was applied.

A half model as shown in Fig. 2(a) was used for the FEA in consideration of symmetry, and an internal pressure of 100 MPa was applied to the inner wall of the tank. 10-node tetrahedral two-dimensional elements (C3D10) were used to the tank head and the dome part of the liner, and 8-node hexahedral reduced integration elements (C3D8R) were applied to the axial member, cylinder, and circular head of the liner.

Table 1 Material Properties of CFRP (T800S/Epoxy)

Properties		Values
Elastic moduli [GPa]	E_L	168.0
	$E_T = E_Z$	10.0
Shear moduli [GPa]	$G_{LT} = G_{LZ}$	6.06
	G_{TZ}	5.0
Poisson's ratio [-]	$\nu_{LT} = \nu_{LZ}$	0.31
	ν_{TZ}	0.45
Tensile strength [MPa]		3290
Failure strain [%]		1.96

2. 3 STRESS ANALYSIS RESULTS

Figures 2(a) and (b) show contour plots of the maximum principal stress in the entire tank and in the cylinder section at an internal pressure of 100 MPa, respectively. As per the design concept, it can be seen that the axial load is mainly carried by the two belt-shaped axial load members, while the circumferential load is carried by the CFRP hoop layer of the cylinder. The circumferential tensile stress is high in the central part of the cylinder, but this is because the CFRP hoop layer is thin (1.6 mm) around here. At an internal pressure of 100 MPa, the axial strain in the general part of the axial load member was 1.25 %, and the strain in the hoop direction in the cylinder CFRP layer was 1.19 %.

Fig.2 Contour plot of max principal stress at the internal pressure of 100 MPa

Fig. 3 shows the maximum principal stress distribution in the axial member when the internal pressure is 100 MPa. The axial stress in the general part of the axial member is 2083 MPa (strain 1.25 %), while the maximum principal stress around the straight line-arc boundary is 2446 MPa (strain 1.47%), which is about 17 % higher. This is because in this area, bending load is superimposed on the tensile load. In addition, watching the straight line-circular arc boundary of the axial load member in Fig. 3, the maximum principal stress is about 4% higher in the lower part (2446 MPa) than in the upper part (2351 MPa). In other words, the axial member has stress distribution in the width direction as well. Fig. 4(a) shows the distribution of the von Mises stress of the tank head when the internal pressure is 100 MPa, and Fig. 4(b) shows the deformation diagram and contour diagram of the z-direction (lateral) displacement. The z-direction displacement is about 0.12 mm larger in the lower part of the tank head compared to the upper part at the contact part of the axial member. In other words, it can be understood that the bending deformation of the tank head causes uneven load distribution on the axial member, and the tensile stress is high in the lower part of the axial member.

In the tank designed this time, it was predicted that the axial load member would break at an internal pressure lower than that of the hoop layer. In addition, based on the tensile strength of UD-CFRP (3290 MPa), it was predicted that the pressure at which the axial load member would break would be approximately 133 MPa.

Fig.3 Contour plot of maximum principal stress of axial load member at the internal pressure of 100 MPa.

Fig.4 Contour plot of Mises stress and z-displacement of tank head at the internal pressure of 100 MPa.

Fig. 5(a) presents the longitudinal strain in the cylinder surface at internal pressures of 27 MPa, 64 MPa, and 100 MPa, respectively. Axial compressive strain appears in the cylinder at the boundary between the cylinder and the tank head. Fig. 5(b) shows the deformation diagram of the tank cross section at an internal pressure of 64 MPa. At the boundary where the longitudinal out-of-plane stiffness differs, out-of-plane bending deformation of the cylinder occurs due to the internal pressure, which can be seen to cause localized compressive strain. For the same reason, localized compressive strain is also observed at each end of the pad-up of the cylinder. Localized out-of-plane deformation also appears in the center of the cylinder, where the hoop thickness is thin, due to the difference in bending stiffness before and after it.

(a) Contour plot of longitudinal strain in the cylinder surface at the internal pressure of 27, 64, and 100 MPa. The deformation magnification is 20 times.

(b) Deformation showing the cross section at the internal pressure of 64 MPa.

Fig.5 Contour plot of longitudinal strain in the cylinder

3. EVALUATION OF TANK PROTOTYPES THROUGH BURST TESTS

3.1. TANK PROTOTYPE

The CFRP hoop layer was formed by wrapping CF/Epoxy Towpreg in the hoop direction around a cylindrical liner made of Al alloy (A6061-T6) using the FW method. The belt-shaped axial force member was also produced by FW forming of Towpreg. The cylinder liner and tank head were produced by machining from Al alloy (A6061-T6) blocks using an NC milling cutter. A photograph of the appearance after assembly is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig.6 Photograph of a tank prototype

3.2. BURST TEST PROCEDURE

A water pressure burst test was carried out in accordance with ISO19881, with a target pressure rise rate of 0.3 MPa. Multiple strain gauges (WFCA-6-11-10LDBTB-F, Tokyo Sokki, Japan) were attached to the surfaces of the cylinder and axial load member, and strain at each part during pressurization was measured with a data logger (EDX-10, Kyowa Denki, Japan). Strain was measured in the hoop direction and axial direction of the cylinder, and in the axial direction at the center of the axial load member and above and below the straight line-arc boundary. In addition, damage and burst behavior of the tank during the test was photographed using a camera (Hero 10, GoPro, USA) installed in the chamber.

3.3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 7 presents the external appearance after the burst. The burst pressure was 99.8 MPa, and the fractured origin was the fiber break of the axial member. The burst pressure was about 75 % of the burst pressure (133 MPa) predicted by the FEA described above. Figure 8 shows photos captured at internal pressures of 0, 72 MPa, and 99.8 MPa from the video taken during the burst test. When the internal pressure exceeded about 50 MPa, audible sounds were heard due to the occurrence and progression of damage in the CFRP. In addition, at an internal pressure of 72 MPa, as shown in Figure 8 (b), separation between fibers (splitting) and partial fiber breakage were confirmed starting from the straight-line-arc boundary of the axial member. This coincides with the location where tensile stress concentration was confirmed in the axial load member in Figure 3. From this damage boundary, many audible sounds were heard due to the occurrence and progression of damage in the CFRP axial load member. As shown in Fig. 8(c), localized splitting and fiber breakage of the axial load member were also observed at another straight-line-arc boundary just before the rupture.

Fig.7 Photographs after burst testing (Burst pressure 99.8 MPa)

Fig.8 Captured images showing the splitting of axial load member.

The attachment positions of the strain gauges (#1-9) on the tank are shown in Fig. 9, and the strain measurement results for the cylinder and axial load member are presented in Fig. 10(a) and (b), respectively. The axial and hoop direction strains of the cylinder hoop layer roughly matched the FEA results. However, the experimental value for the axial strain (strain #2) at the center of the cylinder was much higher compressive strain. This is thought to be due to an error in the attachment position of the strain gauges.

Looking at the axial strain (strain #7) at the center of the axial force member shown in Fig. 10(b), a sudden increase in strain, namely “strain jumping”, can be seen at internal pressures of around 63 MPa, 72 MPa, and 91 MPa. As is clear from the images taken during the burst testing (Fig. 8(b)), local splitting and fiber breakage occurred in the axial load member at the straight-line-arc boundary when the internal pressure was 72 MPa, and this is presumed to be the cause of the strain jump in the axial load member. As mentioned above, bending deformation at the point where the axial member of the tank head is fitted causes a non-uniform stress distribution in the width direction of the axial member, as shown in Fig. 3(a) (b). As a result, in-plane and out-of-plane shear stresses occur in the axial member, and it is believed that splitting occurred due to in-plane interlaminar shear failure.

Fig. 9 Strain gauge installation position

(a) Cylinder

(b) Axial load member

Fig. 10 Strain versus internal pressure

The maximum strain at the time of fracture at the center of the axial member (Strain #7) was 1.63 %. This is approximately 17 % smaller than the fracture strain (1.96 %) of UD-CFRP shown in Table 1. The FEA results show that the maximum strain at the straight-arc boundary is approximately

17 % larger than the strain in the general part of the axial member. Taking these effects into account, when the strain in the general part of the axial member is 1.63 %, the strain at the straight-arc boundary is expected to be approximately 1.9 %. This is 97 % of the fracture strain (1.96 %) of CFRP, which is an appropriate value for the fracture strain of an axial member.

The above suggests that it is important to consider the prevention of splitting due to non-uniform load distribution (shear stress) in the plane and the reduction of stress concentration at the straight-arc boundary when designing axial members.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, with the aim of technically verifying the multi-load path structure concept, we carried out stress analysis, design, prototyping, and evaluation of a tank structure that uses two belt-shaped axial force members and CFRP overwrapped cylinder. It was also investigated the burst behavior and the damage progressive behaviors. As a result, it was verified through analysis and experiments that it is possible to realize a tank structure with a burst pressure roughly as designed by designing a structure in which the internal tank pressure acts directly on the dome part of the tank head. Observation results during the burst test showed that localized splitting and fiber breakage occurred in the axial load members prior to the burst. It was suggested that further increases in burst pressure could be effectively achieved by making the stress acting on the axial load members uniform and by suppressing splitting of the axial load members.

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